

Sulfidation of air-stable iron nanoparticles: A novel strategy how to boost their reactivity demonstrated on Cr(VI) reduction

Viktorie Víchová^{a,b}, Jana Křížek Oborná^b, Martin Petr^b, Jana Soukupová^b, Radka Pechancová^c, Tomáš Pluháček^c, Jan Filip^{b,*}

^a Department of Experimental Physics, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 17. listopadu 1192/12, 771 46 Olomouc, Czech Republic

^b Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute, Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Palacký University Olomouc, Slechtitelů 27, 783 71 Olomouc, Czech Republic

^c Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 17. listopadu 1192/12, 771 46 Olomouc, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Gamze Varank

Keywords:

Sulfidation
Core-shell nZVI particles
Hexavalent chromium
Water remediation
On-site application

ABSTRACT

Sulfidated zero-valent iron nanoparticles (S-nZVI) have been extensively studied as environmentally promising alternative material, which enables reduction of variety of extremely dangerous pollutants directly in the environment. However, synthesis and manipulation with these extremely reactive/pyrophoric nZVI particles represents a challenge and requires special precautions. In this study, we report a synthesis of S-nZVI from air-stable core-shell nZVI, which reactivity with contaminants and properties are comparable with the commonly prepared S-nZVI particles (where the precursor was bare/pyrophoric nZVI particles). The undeniable novelty dwells in the simplicity of the synthetic process, which ensures consequential safe and easy handling, manipulation, and application of S-nZVI particles. This material, especially highly effective against halogenated organic compounds and heavy metals, was characterized in detail and its advanced characteristics were evaluated in the process of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) reduction from model aqueous solutions and polluted groundwater. The results offer valuable insights into the preparation of a novel nanomaterial with high application potential in the effective degradation of heavy metals in polluted water. Overall, the novel way prepared S-nZVI particles, designed for the potential large-scale production, eliminates the drawbacks of S-nZVI synthesized from bare nZVI particles and offers the effective material suitable for any on-site application.

1. Introduction

Nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI) particles emerged as a highly effective material for pollutant degradation, which is widely demonstrated with the capability to facilitate fast Cr(VI) reduction [1–3]. The nZVI particles, with different surface functionalizations, are nowadays commonly used also for the degradation of halogenated organic compounds [4]. Compared to conventionally used chemical remediation technologies, nZVI particles possess numerous advantages, such as a large specific surface area (due to its nanosize dimension) offering sufficient reactive sites thanks to which the reactivity of such a material is high. The nZVI particles exhibit magnetic properties that can be understood as both positive and negative features – thanks to the magnetic character they can be easily manipulated/eliminated in/from the environment but exactly the same feature contributes to the increased aggregation tendencies, possibly leading to mobility limitations, that are

typical for this unmodified nanomaterial [5]. The selectivity of nZVI-based materials still represents a challenge which has not been completely solved yet. To enhance the remediation potential of the nZVI particles, various modifications and surface functionalizations have been investigated [6–11]. A typical example of nZVI surface modification is a coating with either organic substances [7], oxides [8], sulfides [4,9], or carbides [10], as well as the nZVI particles deposition on suitable solid substrates like e.g. biochar [11]. Moreover, the effect of combination of the nZVI particles with different remediation techniques such as bioremediation [12] or electric field [13] has also been studied and subsequently implemented in technologies of groundwater restoration. In the last decade rather, intensive studies have been devoted to the sulfidation of nZVI particles (S-nZVI) as the performed functionalization mitigates the drawbacks associated with bare nZVI [14,15]. The increased hydrophobicity of the S-nZVI particles [16–18] results in slower aggregation of the particles [19], regulated electron transfer from

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jan.filip@upol.cz (J. Filip).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.106246>

Received 25 June 2024; Received in revised form 25 September 2024; Accepted 25 September 2024

Available online 3 October 2024

2214-7144/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

the iron core [9,14] and hydrogen recombination [20,21]. Due to these properties, the S-nZVI particles enable enhanced selective decontamination of remediated site from a variety of both inorganic and organic pollutants such as e.g. chlorinated compounds [9,16], or heavy metal (loid)s [4,22,23]. On the top of this fact, the nZVI particles are able to inactivate even potentially dangerous biological material such as bacteria [24].

The preparation of S-nZVI particles can be achieved through a one-pot or a complex synthetic process [15]. In the one-pot synthesis, bare nZVI particles are synthesized by mixing ferrous/ferric ions in solution with an effective reducing agent (e.g. NaBH_4). Subsequently, a sulfidation agent (e.g. Na_2S) is added to the system [25]. The choice of sulfur precursor in the synthesis of S-nZVI is a critical factor that can significantly influence the structural and chemical properties of the resulting material [26–28]. For example, the use of dithionite ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$) as a precursor has been reported to produce S-nZVI with greater long-term stability due to the formation of more stable iron sulfide phases [27,28]. In this study, we employed sodium sulfide (Na_2S) as the sulfur precursor, consistent with our previous work [4,9], to maintain comparability across our research. Choong et al. [29] prepared S-nZVI particle suspension via such a one-pot synthesis, in a 200 L container in the laboratory, which was then transported to the site of application. Such a large volume represents a logistics challenge also connected with undesired transport and safety expenses. Therefore, from economic, environmental and hazard preventing reasons, the on-site preparation of the material right prior to the application is therefore preferred [30]. The second option of S-nZVI particle preparation represents fundamentally two steps – i) preparation of the nZVI particles (via borohydride reduction/thermal reduction of iron oxide/oxyhydroxide precursors in reductive atmosphere etc.) followed with ii) sulfidation of the nZVI particles. Although the process resembles the first one, as it proceeds in two different phases, it cannot be performed as the previously presented one-pot synthesis. However, as the S-nZVI particles are meant to be used in a large-scale, on-site application, this approach is more suitable. The commercially available nZVI particles can be independently sulfidated on-site according to the specific site parameters - in any concentrations and volumes. Nevertheless, sulfidation of nZVI particles requires a highly specialized procedure because of the pyrophoric nature of the material. The prepared S-nZVI particles are, in a form of highly reactive suspensions, then transported to the field for application. Brumovský et al. [4] reported a commercially available S-nZVI suspension produced through a two-step synthesis (thermal reduction of iron oxide precursors in H_2 atmosphere followed with a sulfidation procedure). However, they also reported that the sulfidation process was performed at the suppliers' site and they had to transport the total amount of 370 L of the S-nZVI particle suspension to the application site. Although Brumovský et al. prepared highly efficient material, the logistics challenges and a long idle period between the preparation and the site application are against the efficiency of the material [31].

Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is a pollutant, having undeniable environmental and health impact due its highly toxic, mutagenic and carcinogenic effects [32] which is commonly employed in reactivity studies of any nZVI particles (even with different surface functionalizations, e.g. S-nZVI particles [33,34]). To mitigate harmful impact of this pollutant in the environment, effective strategies for its degradation and removal are investigated, involving physical separation from the contaminated area or in-situ Cr(VI) reduction to its less toxic and less mobile form, to Cr(III) [35]. This form of less toxic chromium can form complexes with e.g. iron (oxyhydr)oxides [36]. Currently, the most promising remediation methods for Cr(VI) removal include chemical reduction [37–39], adsorption [40,41] and photocatalytic methods [42,43]. Moreover, alternative methods for heavy metal removal have emerged, such as electrokinetic remediation [44,45] or the usage of an electromagnetic field [46]. The approach that uses chemical reduction of Cr(VI) and subsequential immobilization of Cr(III) has proved to be highly promising in environmental remediations and is most commonly

performed with nZVI particles [47]. However, the introduction of an effective, easily applicable, and convenient approach to in-situ remediation still represents a challenge.

The aim of this study was to introduce a novel, scalable method for preparing S-nZVI particle suspensions, which would react to the above-mentioned drawbacks and eliminate them. The S-nZVI particle suspensions have to fulfil the following requirements: i) reproducible synthesis with a potential of large-scale production, ii) straightforward on-site activation/fabrication from the air-stable (passivated) core-shell nZVI particle system, and iii) high efficiency in Cr(VI) degradation, all together leading to reduction of logistics costs and demands during field operations. We successfully achieved all of the predetermined goals, as demonstrated by the comprehensive characterization of the material's physicochemical properties and its reactivity with model pollutant Cr(VI) – either present in groundwater samples or prepared as a laboratory sample. This new approach not only overcomes the challenges of traditional S-nZVI synthesis but also offers a practical and efficient solution for environmental remediation, paving the way for widespread application.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material preparation

2.1.1. Activation process of air-stable nZVI

The activation of the oxide-passivated core-shell nZVI particles (purchased as NANO FER STAR from NANO IRON s.r.o., Czech Republic) represents an essential procedure, which restores the reactivity of the nZVI particles. The activation process was adopted from Ribas et al. [48]. Briefly, the core-shell nZVI particles were dispersed in distilled water to prepare 25% w/v suspension in glass vials. The nZVI particle suspensions were intensively mixed using a dispersing instrument T25 ULTRA-TURRAX® (IKA, Staufen, Germany) in the following sequence: 1 min ON – 1 min OFF (to allow nanoparticles to settle down) – 1 min ON at 11,000 rpm. Afterwards, the vials with the nZVI particle suspensions were sealed and stored at laboratory temperature for 36 h.

2.1.2. Sulfidation of nZVI

The procedure of nZVI particle sulfidation was adopted from the previously published studies carried out by researchers from Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute, Palacký University [4,9]. Briefly, the preparation of a 25% w/v suspension proceeded as follows: 5 g of nZVI particles was added into 20 mL of distilled water. The sulfidation agent ($\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98.0% purity, ThermoFisher, USA) was added to the vials and then the vials were shaken for one hour on a 360° multi-functional tube rotator (PTR-60, Grant USA INC., USA) to perform the sulfidation of the nZVI particles. The sulfidation procedure, functionalizing the surface of the particles, was performed with three different types of nZVI particles: i) pyrophoric nZVI particles (NANO FER 25P, labelled as **S-nZVI_p**), ii) non-activated core-shell nZVI particles (NANO FER STAR, labelled as **S-nZVI_{NAC}**), iii) activated core-shell nZVI particles (NANO FER STAR, labelled as **S-nZVI_{Ac}**). The S-nZVI_{NAC} particles were employed into the study to highlight the impact of the activation process on the reactivity of the material. The sulfidation process was performed in three different S/Fe mass ratios: 0.005, 0.01 and 0.025. These ratios were chosen according to the previously conducted studies [4,9]. For the reactivity tests with Cr(VI) , the S-nZVI particle suspensions were used without any further modification.

Prior the reactivity experiments, the suspensions of S-nZVI were mixed for 2 min at 11,000 rpm using a dispersing instrument and then added to the solution to achieve a concentration equal to 0.2, 0.5 or 2 g/L of the S-nZVI particles in the suspensions. The pH of the dispersions after the addition of the nZVI suspensions were adjusted to the value of 7 using 1% HCl only in the case of experiments held in distilled water.

2.2. Aging of S-nZVI

The prepared S-nZVI suspensions were left to age for 14 days to verify the stability of the material in water and the presence of air and simulate thus real conditions during field applications. S-nZVI suspensions were prepared according to previous section. The sulfidation was performed in S/Fe mass ratio 0.01 for S-nZVI_p and S-nZVI_{Ac}. Afterwards, the glass vials were tightly closed, a needle was put in the rubber septum in the cap to let evolved hydrogen to release and vials were stored standing in a fume hood under air atmosphere at laboratory temperature. Samples were withdrawn after 1, 5, 11 and 14 days.

2.3. Groundwater from contaminated site

The contaminated site, from which the samples of groundwater were collected, is located in the Northern Moravia region in the Czech Republic. The polluted groundwater originates from an underground borehole in the former industrial area of a light engineering production. A sample of groundwater, taken from this contaminated site, underwent a complete analysis (Table S3). The pH value was 8.34 and Eh value 340 mV. The total hardness was 0.597 mmol/L. The sample contained a high concentration of dissolved sodium (116 mg/L). The dissolved iron was not present (values below LOD). Chromium speciation was performed using ion exchange high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to inductively coupled plasma – mass spectrometry (IE-HPLC-ICP-MS). Cr(VI) was present in the concentration of 21.3 ± 1.7 mg/L.

2.4. Batch experiments with a model contaminant (Cr(VI)) in distilled water, medium hard water, and the polluted groundwater

The Cr(VI) degradation was initially tested in the distilled water (300 mL, 10 mg/L of Cr(VI)), then in medium hard water (MHW) (300 mL, 10 mg/L of Cr(VI)), and polluted groundwater (60 mL, 21.3 ± 1.7 of Cr(VI)). The effectiveness of the S-nZVI_p, S-nZVI_{Ac} and S-nZVI_{NAC} particles on the Cr(VI) degradation was studied in the systems containing the final concentrations of nZVI particles equal to 0.2 g/L for the distilled water, 0.5 g/L for MHW and 2.0 g/L for the polluted groundwater. Slightly higher nZVI concentration, than in the experiment in distilled water and MHW, was used because of the higher concentration of total chromium (Cr_{tot}) in polluted water. S-nZVI with different S/Fe mass ratios (0.005, 0.01 and 0.025) were used in the distilled water. For subsequent experiments (in MHW and polluted groundwater) the ratio of 0.01 was chosen according to its good efficacy in distilled water. All batch experiments were performed in a four-necked round-bottom flask (Fig. S1) with a capacity of 500 mL for the distilled water and MHW, and a three-necked round-bottom flask with a capacity of 100 mL for polluted groundwater, respectively. The flasks were filled up to 60% of the total volume and purged with nitrogen for 30 min before adding the nZVI-derived suspensions to eliminate dissolved oxygen in the solution. Moreover, the flasks were flushed with nitrogen during the experiments, and solutions were permanently mixed (300 rpm) using an overhead stirrer (PTR-60, Grant-bio, GRANT USA INC., USA) with a teflon stirrer. The pH and redox potential (ORP) values were regularly monitored using a multimeter (Multi 3630 IDS, WTW, Germany) equipped with a pH electrode (SenTix® 940, WTW, Germany) and ORP electrode (SenTix® ORP-T 900, WTW, Germany). The data were collected every minute for the first hour and afterwards every hour up to 24 h. The samples for chemical analyses were withdrawn at 2.5, 5, 15, 30, and 60 min and 24 h, and the nZVI particles were separated using magnetic force and filtrated through 0.22 µm PTFE filters (LABICOM s.r.o., Czech Republic). The liquid samples were then analyzed using spectrophotometry, atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), inductively coupled plasma – mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) or IE-HPLC-ICP-MS for the determination of Cr_{tot} concentration or its species. All the experiments were performed in triplicates, and the results are expressed as an arithmetical mean ± standard deviation. The solid samples for X-ray powder diffraction

(XRD) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis of chromium chemical state were withdrawn after 24 h (at the end of the experiment). The XRD analysis was performed immediately and the sample for XPS was directly frozen in liquid N₂ and stored at -20 °C prior the analysis.

2.5. Methods used for material characterization and chemical analyses

Several methods and analytical tools were used for material characterization and determination of total element levels. All the methods are briefly described below and even more details can be found in Supplementary information.

2.5.1. Surface analysis of material

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements by means the VersaProbe II XPS system (Physical Electronics Inc., USA) with a monochromatic Al K α source (photon energy of 1,486.7 eV) was used for determination of the chemical state of sulfur on the surface of nZVI, as well as the chemical state of chromium on the surface of nZVI particles during their reaction with contaminated water.

The surface of nanoparticles and their size and shape were studied with electron microscopes. The transmission electron microscope (TEM) JEM-2100 (JEOL Ltd., Japan) was used for the nZVI particles images obtained at an electron acceleration voltage of 200 kV. High-resolution TEM (HR-TEM), Titan G2 TEM (FEI, USA), operating at 80 kV and equipped with a BM UltraScan CCD camera (Gatan), was used to obtain the images of individual particles. Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS) was performed in Scanning TEM (STEM) mode by Super-X system with four silicon drift detectors (Bruker, USA). STEM images were obtained with HAADF detector 3000 (Fischione, USA).

The hydrodynamic diameter (d_H) of the nZVI particles/aggregates was monitored by the dynamic light scattering (DLS) at the Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument (Malvern PANalytical, UK).

The specific surface area (SSA) of the sample could significantly affect the reactivity of the material. SSA was determined via gas sorption analysis performed by means of N₂ adsorption/desorption measurements at 77 K on a volumetric gas adsorption analyzer (Autosorb iQ XR, Anton-Paar Quanta Tec, USA) up to 0.965 p/p₀.

2.5.2. Determination of phase composition and electromagnetic properties

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) measurement was used to distinguish the crystalline phase in the samples. The measurements were performed with the Aeris diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, Ltd., USA) operating in Bragg-Brentano geometry.

The magnetization measurements were performed using a physical property measurement system (PPMS) magnetometer (Quantum Design, USA). Hysteresis loops were recorded at 300 K under the external magnetic fields ranging from $-50,000$ Oe to $50,000$ Oe.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed to evaluate the charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) of prepared materials. All EIS spectra were collected using a 5 mV amplitude and were recorded over the frequency range 0.1 Hz to 10 kHz using the half-wave potential of potassium ferricyanide(III) (0.2 V).

2.5.3. Total element levels determination and calculation of reaction rates

The sulfur bonded on the surface of the nZVI particles was determined using elemental analysis. The CHNS elementary analysis was performed using a Thermo Scientific Flash 2000 analyzer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The samples were measured three times and the average value is presented.

The Cr(VI) concentration changes were evaluated via fast colorimetric test [49] with 1,5-diphenylcarbazine using a UV-visible scanning spectrophotometer Lightwave II (WPA, Biochrom Ltd., UK).

The residual Cr_{tot} concentrations, both in the experiments in distilled water or in MHW, were determined with atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) using the ContraAA 600 spectrometer (Analytik Jena,

Germany) with electrothermal atomization and Xe continuous radiation source.

Cr_{tot} concentration in the experiments in groundwater and sulfur (S) levels in the solutions after the sulfidation were determined with 7700x ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies, Japan). The S level was quantified directly in the water solution, whereas the samples for the Cr_{tot} level determination were acidified with 6% (v/v) nitric acid in order to dissolve all chromium species. The regular measurement of the independently prepared quality control sample at 5 mg/L for S and 100 μ g/L for Cr was adopted to ensure the reliability of ICP-MS results. All samples were measured in six technical replicates.

The chromium oxidation state in experiments with groundwater was revealed by IE-HPLC-ICP-MS after the extraction of soluble Cr(III) and total Cr(VI) using 100 mmol/L EDTA with pH value of 10.5. All the speciation analyses were performed using a hyphenation of Agilent 1290 Infinity II HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with 7700x ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies, Japan) using 9 points external calibration. The chromium species were separated on a strong anion exchange Dionex Ion Pac™ AG7 Guard column (PEEK, 2 × 50 mm, 10 μ m, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Courtaboeuf, France) column using a mobile phase composed of 60 mmol/L NH_4NO_3 and 0.6 mmol/L EDTA in ultrapure water (pH 7.2) with a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The IE-HPLC-ICP-MS derived chromium species interconversion was monitored by the adoption of $^{50}Cr(VI)$ isotopically enriched standard. The regular measurements of the independently prepared quality control sample at 100 μ g/L for both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) were used to ensure the reliability of IE-HPLC-ICP-MS results. All samples were measured in triplicates.

The kinetics during the batch tests with Cr(VI) in distilled water followed the pseudo-second-order type of reaction. The pseudo-second-order reaction rate constants k_{OBS} were calculated using Eq. (1)

$$q_t = \frac{q_e^2 k_{OBS} t}{1 + q_e k_{OBS} t} \quad (1)$$

where q_t is the amount adsorbed in time, q_e amount remaining after the equilibrium of absorption reaction and t is time.

The initial surface-area-normalized rate constants, k_{SA} , were obtained from Eq. (2)

$$k_{SA} = \frac{k_{OBS}}{\alpha_s \rho_m} \quad (2)$$

where k_{OBS} is pseudo-second-order reaction rate constant, α_s is the surface area of the particles (m^2/g) and ρ_m is the particle dosage (g/L). The reaction constants were calculated only for sulfidated activated core-shell nZVI particles (S-nZVI_{Ac}) and sulfidated bare nZVI particles (S-nZVI_p) in distilled water as the Cr(VI) degradation by S-nZVI closely followed pseudo-second-order kinetics.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Formation of sulfide shell on the nZVI particle surface

The sulfur shell made of iron sulfides formed on nZVI particles plays a dual role in both stabilizing the iron core and modulating reactivity. The sulfidation process was carried out for each type of the nZVI particles with the difference in S/Fe mass ratios (i.e., 0.005, 0.01 and 0.025): **sulfidated non-activated core-shell nZVI particles** (S-nZVI_{NAC}), **sulfidated activated core-shell nZVI particles** (S-nZVI_{Ac}) and **sulfidated bare nZVI particles** (S-nZVI_p). The differences in sulfur content among the different nZVI particle types provided undeniable important insights into the effectiveness of the sulfidation process and the importance of the activation process of the core-shell nZVI particles. Therefore, the sulfur on their surface and the residual sulfur in the solutions after the sulfidation were determined (Figs. 1 and S2, Table S4). Notably, solutions used for preparation of S-nZVI_{NAC} particles exhibited a significant amount of dissolved sulfur after the sulfidation process (Fig. 1B), suggesting limited sulfidation of nZVI particle surface compared to the other types of S-nZVI. These results are supported by elemental analysis, which detected no sulfur present in the case of S-nZVI_{NAC} particles with the S/Fe mass ratios of 0.005 and 0.01 (Fig. 1A). Based on a detailed analysis of the sulfur 2p core-level spectra using XPS, notable variations among samples were observed, with each presenting unique characteristics in their sulfur speciation (Fig. S2). In the case of S-nZVI_{NAC} particles, no discernible S 2p lines were detected for S/Fe 0.005 and 0.01 (Fig. S2A, D). On contrary, the S-nZVI_{NAC} particles with the S/Fe ratio equal to 0.025 indicates the presence of S^{2-} in accordance with elemental analysis (Figs. S2G, 1A). These findings demonstrate that the iron sulfides were not formed on the surface of such type of nZVI particles, at least not to a significant extent (approximately 1% instead of 2.5%). When we compare the S-nZVI_p particles and S-nZVI_{Ac} particles, with low concentrations of sulfur in the solutions (i.e., for S/Fe ratio 0.005 and 0.01) (Fig. 1B), most of the sulfur was successfully reduced on the surface of the nanoparticles forming a compact shell as further confirmed by elemental analysis (Fig. 1A) and this observation is in full accordance with previously conducted studies [4,9]. However, when S/Fe mass ratio was increased to 0.025, the S-nZVI_p particles and S-nZVI_{Ac} particles start to differ from each other. The solid S-nZVI_{Ac} particles contains the mass percentage of sulfur used in the reaction, and the residual sulfur in the solution corresponds to this. On the contrary, during the reaction leading to formation of S-nZVI_p a certain amount of sulfur remains in the dispersing medium (Fig. 1B), which is corresponding with the lower sulfur content quantified by elemental analysis. It simply implies that not all sulfur was reduced on the nZVI particle surface. The XPS spectra of S-nZVI_{Ac} particles and S-nZVI_p particles indicate almost identical presence of sulfur in the oxidation state S^{2-} , i.e. at a binding energy of 162.0 eV for all S/Fe mass ratios (Fig. S2). Importantly, variations in sulfur speciation can lead to differences in reactivity and stability of S-nZVI, affecting its

Fig. 1. A – sulfur content in the variously sulfidated nZVI particles measured with CHNS analysis; B – sulfur content in the aqueous solutions after the sulfidation of nZVI particles measured with ICP-MS. The data are presented as the arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation of independently prepared triplicates.

environmental performance [27,28].

The surface morphology of the synthesized S-nZVI particles was examined using TEM (Fig. 2A–C). The S-nZVI particles of different types exhibited slight changes in their surface structure. In the case of the S-nZVI_{NAC}, the surface oxidative shell is clearly visible (Fig. 2B); however, in the case of the S-nZVI_{Ac} particle surface, incomplete shell side by side with flat structures were observed. This phenomenon is undoubtedly caused by the activation process. Due to the reaction of the nZVI particles with water the oxide shell is broken and the process is followed by the generation of iron(II) hydroxides forming flat-layered crystals and

lamellae around the nZVI particles [48,50]. HR-TEM (Fig. 2D–F) provided insight into the structure of the shell but with no clear difference between the sulfide shell and the oxide shell. TEM measurements with elemental distribution mapping (STEM-EDS) (Fig. 2G–L), used for differentiation of the overlapping sulfide shell and oxide shell, revealed variations in sulfur distribution. The images of the S-nZVI_p particles (Fig. 2I, L) and S-nZVI_{Ac} particles (Fig. 2H, K) exhibited a uniform sulfur layer when compared to S-nZVI_{NAC} particles (Fig. 2G, J), where sulfur is present in a low abundance without formation of distinct sulfide shell. It was also confirmed with the STEM-EDS mapping (Fig. S3, Table S6).

Fig. 2. TEM images (A–C), HR-TEM images (D–F), STEM-EDS maps (G–L) of the sulfidated nZVI particles with S/Fe ratio of 0.01: S-nZVI_{NAC} particles (A, D, G, J), S-nZVI_{Ac} particles (B, E, H, K) and S-nZVI_p particles (C, F, I, L).

These findings correspond with the results obtained from ICP-MS analysis of dissolved sulfur in sulfidation solutions and CHNS analysis (Fig. 1, Table S4).

The potential impact of the performed modification process on the mobility of the particles/aggregates was evaluated by the measurements of particle/aggregate diameter in their natural environment – in the highly concentrated system. The dispersions, with the 25% w/v of nZVI particles, represent truly highly concentrated dispersion, where effective collisions of the primarily prepared particles are highly probable and followed by the formation of aggregates (Fig. 2A–C). The TEM images cannot completely describe the situation in the system because of the way of the TEM sample preparation when the media has to be evaporated and therefore some of the images can refer to the formation of larger aggregates just because of the drying process. Compared to that, the DLS measurement offers a more realistic insight into the global nZVI particle behavior because the particles/particle aggregates remain in the dispersing media (Table S7). The DLS measurements confirmed the presence of aggregates/agglomerates in all of the measured systems, i.e. system of S-nZVI_{NAC} particles, S-nZVI_{AC} particles, and S-nZVI_{IP} particles and all the S/Fe ratios used for the sulfidation. The hydrodynamic diameters (d_H) of the detected objects (aggregates/agglomerates) in the prepared systems varied, according to the intensity mode of the DLS measurements, from 790 nm to approx. 2 μm (Table S7), without any traceable dependency on the type of the preparation (core-shell – activated vs. non-activated vs. pyrophoric) or the degree of the performed surface functionalization. However, there were detected two exceptions. In the systems of the non-activated core-shell particles (S-nZVI_{NAC}), with the 0.01 and 0.025 S/Fe mass ratio, the majority of the particle aggregates/agglomerates exhibited hydrodynamic diameter of 118 nm and 160 nm, respectively. These systems revealed to develop just low abundance of sulfur surface functionalization but still even a low amount of sulfur evidently contributed to different aggregation behavior of the whole system. Interestingly, both of these systems exhibited also significantly lower efficiency in Cr(VI) removal rates after 24 h (compared to the other two systems with comparable surface modification; see Section 3.4).

3.2. The effect of sulfidation on structural and electromagnetic properties of nZVI particles

The metallic iron (Fe^0) content is directly related to the reductive capacity of the S-nZVI particles. A higher Fe^0 content generally indicates a greater potential for contaminant interaction and elimination [8]. In this study, the Fe^0 crystalline content ($\alpha\text{-Fe}$, bcc structure) was quantified using Rietveld analysis from XRD patterns, ensuring that the iron core content is sufficient to drive effective redox reactions, which are essential for the applications in e.g. Cr(VI) reduction. The structural and phase changes of the S-nZVI particles compared to the non-activated and the activated core-shell nZVI particles were evaluated using XRD. Three crystalline phases were identified in all samples (Fig. S4, Table S8). A major phase was $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ (Fe^0) with an average content of 96 wt.% in samples, magnetite (Fe_3O_4) (4 wt.%) and wüstite (FeO) (<1 wt.%) were identified as minor phases. In any of S-nZVI particles, the crystalline phases of iron sulfide were not confirmed. This was caused by the limited sulfur content in the system as well as the presence of iron sulfide in poorly crystalline or amorphous form [4,9,34] as a thin shell. In previous studies dealing with sulfidation of analogous nZVI particles, the sulfides forming such shell were identified as poorly crystalline mackinawite [4,9]. $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ (96 wt.%), magnetite (4 wt.%) and wüstite (<1 wt.%) were detected as main/minor crystalline phases also for all the non-sulfidated types of nZVI particles (Fig. S4, Table S8) in accordance with the previously published studies [8].

The formation of a sulfide shell on the nZVI surface slightly affected also the specific surface area of the particles (Table S9). The SSA of the S-ZVI_{NAC} particles are comparable for all sulfur ratios and with the precursor (nZVI_{NAC} particles) which corresponds with the finding that the

compact sulfide shell was not extensively formed on their surface (see Section 3.1). In the case of S-ZVI_{IP} particles and S-ZVI_{AC} particles, the SSA varies between 22 and 39 m^2/g . For S-ZVI_{IP} particles, the SSA decreased with an increasing sulfur ratio as observed already in previous studies [9]. On the contrary, the increasing trend in the SSA with an increasing sulfur dose was observed for S-ZVI_{AC} particles. This can be attributed to the formation of iron corrosion products on the nZVI particle surface [9].

The sulfidation has also an effect on the magnetic characteristics of the nZVI particles. According to hysteresis curves of magnetic measurements (Fig. S5), the sulfidated nZVI particles, with the S/Fe ratio of 0.01, are ferromagnetic and reach a high magnetic saturation value of around 150 emu/g (Table S10). The S-nZVI particles prepared from the core-shell structured particles of nZVI (NFSTAR) showed a wider hysteresis curve compared to S-nZVI_{IP} prepared from bare nZVI (NF25P) resulting in a decrease in saturation magnetization. Such a feature could be only explained by the presence of non-ferromagnetic or less ferromagnetic iron oxides in the shell (magnetite and wüstite as confirmed with XRD in Fig. S4 and Table S8) [8,50].

The electron-transfer resistance is another key factor that influences the kinetics of the contaminant reduction using the surface-modified nZVI particles [51]. The electrochemical behavior of sulfidated nZVI particles with S/Fe mass ratio of 0.01 was studied using EIS (Figs. S6, S7). The results indicate a significant increase in charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) when the working GC electrode ($R_{CT} = 376 \Omega$) was modified with the precursors of S-nZVI particles: nZVI_{AC} ($R_{CT} = 565 \Omega$), nZVI_{NAC} ($R_{CT} = 706 \Omega$), or nZVI_{IP} sample ($R_{CT} = 974 \Omega$). This behavior suggests successful immobilization of all the tested materials on the electrode surface, providing insights into the properties of the individual samples. The various behavior was observed for sulfidated nZVI particles. Notably, the lowest R_{CT} value was observed for the S-nZVI_{NAC} particles ($R_{CT} = 816 \Omega$), which corresponds with the unsuccessful sulfidation confirmed by XPS (see above). On contrary, the highest R_{CT} value for the S-nZVI_{IP} particles ($R_{CT} = 2,010 \Omega$) indicates a thicker sulfide layer compared to the S-nZVI_{AC} particles ($R_{CT} = 1,020 \Omega$). These observations are in a good agreement with the images from the electron microscopy (see above) and with previous studies [52].

3.3. The effect of aging on the surface properties of S-nZVI particles

Minor structural and phase composition changes were observed during the aging process of the S-nZVI_{AC} and S-nZVI_{IP} suspensions with S/Fe mass ratio of 0.01 (i.e. in the sodium sulfide solution). Iron (II) hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$) was formed on the surface and in the proximity of the nanoparticles, which can be clearly recognized as flat-layered crystals and lamellae that surround the nanoparticles in the TEM images (Fig. 3C, D). The presence of iron (II) hydroxide was further confirmed by XRD analysis (Fig. 3A, B). In the course of 14 days, the amount of the iron core ($\alpha\text{-Fe}$) decreased (Table S11), which clearly demonstrates the conversion of elemental iron to iron hydroxides. Such transformations are typical for nZVI aging, as the iron core gradually reacts and oxidizes in an aqueous solution [48,50]. The changes in crystalline phase occurred more rapidly for S-nZVI_{AC} compared to S-nZVI_{IP}. This behavior can be attributed to the pre-existing iron (hydr)oxide shell, which accelerates the growth of the iron(II) hydroxides. However, based on a detailed XPS analysis of the sulfur 2p core-level spectra, no significant changes in sulfur speciation were observed (Fig. 3E, F). Sulfur was consistently present in S^{2-} state, as in the freshly prepared S-nZVI samples (Fig. S2E, F). No oxidized sulfur species were detected to indicate that the sulfide shell did not undergo significant aging (oxidation) process over time.

3.4. The effect of sulfidation of nZVI on the reduction of Cr(VI)

3.4.1. The Cr(VI) degradation in distilled and medium hard water

Hexavalent chromium was selected as a representative contaminant to demonstrate the impact of sulfidation on the nZVI particle reactivity.

Fig. 3. The impact of aging of S-nZVI on their properties: the comparison of diffractograms of S-nZVI with S/Fe ratio of 0.01 in for S-nZVI_{Ac} (A) and S-nZVI_P (B) in time, TEM images of aged nanoparticles after 14 days for S-nZVI_{Ac} (C) and S-nZVI_P (D) and high-resolution XPS spectra from S 2p region for S-nZVI_{Ac} (E) and S-nZVI_P (F) after 14 days.

The results of Cr(VI) elimination **from distilled water** revealed variations in reactivity among different types of sulfidated nZVI particles, which corresponded to the difference with the sulfur-to-iron ratio (Figs. S8, S9). Overall, the non-activated (S-nZVI_{NAC}) particles exhibited notably low efficiency, achieving decrease in Cr_{TOT} concentration by 13% (S/Fe mass ratio 0.005), 30% (S/Fe mass ratio 0.01) and 51% (S/Fe mass ratio 0.025) after 24 h. However, the efficiency of nZVI_{NAC} particles towards Cr(VI) (3% removal, Fig. S9) increased due to the sulfidation process even though the presence of the sulfide on their surface was confirmed only for S-nZVI_{NAC} particles with the S/Fe mass ratio equal to 0.025. This can be ascribed to the generally low abundance of sulfide on the nZVI particle surface, which was not detectable with XPS or any other methods. In contrast, originally pyrophoric and activated (S-nZVI_P and S-nZVI_{Ac} respectively) particles demonstrated greater efficacy in eliminating Cr(VI) from the solution and exhibited comparable trends throughout the experiment (Fig. S8A–D). The kinetics of Cr(VI) removal by S-nZVI_{Ac} particles and S-nZVI_P particles in distilled water followed

the trend of second-order reaction. The calculated pseudo-second-order rate constants (k_{OBS}) (Table 1) increased with the S/Fe mass ratio. Even though k_{OBS} for S-nZVI_P particles were slightly higher than for S-nZVI_{Ac} particles, their reaction rates are comparable. Although the S-nZVI_{Ac} particles with S/Fe ratio equal to 0.025 exhibited slightly slower kinetics of Cr(VI) removal ($k_{OBS} = 12.7 \pm 2.3$) than S-nZVI_P particles

Table 1

Cr(VI) reaction kinetics calculated from the experiments in distilled water ($c_{S-nZVI} = 0.2$ g/L).

Material	k_{OBS} (10^{-3} h ⁻¹)	BET SSA (m ² /g)	k_{SA} (10^{-3} h ⁻¹)
S-nZVI _{Ac} .0.005	7.2 ± 0.3	26	1.3 ± 0.1
S-nZVI _P .0.005	6.0 ± 0.8	39	0.7 ± 0.1
S-nZVI _{Ac} .0.010	8.5 ± 1.1	29	1.5 ± 0.2
S-nZVI _P .0.010	12.4 ± 2.8	26	2.4 ± 0.5
S-nZVI _{Ac} .0.025	12.7 ± 2.3	38	1.6 ± 0.3
S-nZVI _P .0.025	18.7 ± 3.0	25	4.5 ± 0.7

($k_{OBS} = 18.7 \pm 3.0$), they successfully eliminated almost all Cr(VI), i.e. 97%, from the tested solution within 24 h (Fig. S8D).

Subsequently, the sulfidated nZVI particles with a S/Fe ratio equal to 0.01 were evaluated for the Cr(VI) elimination **from medium hard water** (Fig. S8C). This S/Fe ratio was chosen because the same material proved high efficiency for Cr(VI) elimination from distilled water and the aqueous suspension does not contain excessive dissolved sulfur after the sulfidation process (Fig. 1B, Table S4). The efficiency of the S-nZVI_{NAC} particles was 56%, 100% for the S-nZVI_{AC} particles and similar for the S-nZVI_P during the 24 h application.

The amount of Cr_{tot} in the aqueous samples withdrawn during the experiment (quantified using AAS, Fig. S8) is nearly equivalent to the concentration of hexavalent chromium, suggesting the elimination of Cr(VI) via adsorption, followed by its reduction on the surface of nZVI to Cr(III) and the potential subsequent precipitation of Cr(III) with iron. Notably, the iron oxides present on the surface of S-nZVI could also participate in this Cr(VI) removal mechanism. These oxides provide an adsorptive surface for pollutants [53,54], creating an environment where the reduction of Cr(VI) can occur.

In order to shed more light on the mechanism of the interaction between the dissolved/present Cr(VI) and the functionalized surface of nZVI particles, high-resolution XPS over the chromium 2p_{3/2} region was analyzed (Fig. S10). In all types of S-nZVI particles after the reaction with Cr(VI), two distinctively different chromium based compounds were identified: Cr(III) as hydroxide and Cr(III) as oxide. The Cr(III) in the form of hydroxide(s) was characterized by a single band at a binding energy of approx. 577.1 eV. In contrast, the Cr(III) in the form of oxide(s) state was deconvoluted into a multiplet comprising up to five bands, in accordance with the previous studies [55]. For all samples with an S/Fe mass ratio of 0.01, up to 57% of the chromium was present as Cr(III) hydroxide and the rest as Cr(III) oxide. No Cr(VI) was detected in any of the collected spectra, i.e. on the surface of S-nZVI particles. These findings confirm that all primarily adsorbed Cr(VI) was completely reduced to Cr(III) and immobilized on the surface of nZVI in the form of chromium(III)-iron (hydr)oxides [4,47]. The XRD did not reveal any crystalline chromium-bearing phase(s) (Fig. S11) in all analyzed samples.

For comparison, Cr(VI) removal rate was studied also for nZVI_{AC} particles and nZVI_{NAC} particles (i.e. core-shell nZVI particles without sulfidation) (Fig. S9). Such observations unambiguously confirm that the sulfidation led to a significant improvement of the nZVI particle reactivity with Cr(VI). The role of the dissolved sulfur in the solution where Cr(VI) removal proceeded, was inspected through the experiment with filtrated solution from sulfidation of nZVI particles with the S/Fe ratio of 0.025. Almost no changes in chromium concentration were observed using the dissolved sulfur (Fig. S8E). The changes in pH and oxidative-reduction potential (Eh) were also monitored during the experiments (Fig. S12). The evolution of pH followed generally the same trend through experiments for all sulfidated nZVI particles: pH increased at the beginning of the experiment and reached the maximum value at the moment of Cr_{tot} elimination from the suspension (Fig. S8). On the other side, pH changes in the case of S-nZVI_{NAC} particles are not significant, which obviously corresponds to the trend of Cr(VI) degradation. Redox values follow the opposite trend – Eh decreased slightly in the course of Cr(VI) removal and increased afterwards. This behavior can be attributed to the passivation of the nZVI particle surface with chromium-iron (hydr)oxides (Fig. S10), which results in decreased reactivity.

3.4.2. The Cr(VI) elimination from the contaminated groundwater

The batch tests with polluted groundwater from the contaminated site revealed similar trends in the reactivity among different types of sulfidated nZVI particles (Fig. 4A, B) as during batch tests with distilled or MHW. The tests were done only with S-nZVI particles (in concentration of 2.0 g/L) with S/Fe mass ratio of 0.01 according to their good efficacy in previous experiments. The decrease in total

chromium concentration (Cr_{tot}) (measured with ICP-MS, Fig. 4A) was not significant for the non-activated (S-nZVI_{NAC}) particles, achieving the removal by 75% of Cr_{tot} after 24 h. On contrary, the S-nZVI_P particles and the S-nZVI_{AC} particles showed almost complete Cr(VI) degradation and elimination from the solution within less than one hour. Even though the S-nZVI_P particles reached the LOD of the Cr_{tot} concentration after 5 min and the S-nZVI_{AC} particles after approx. 30 min, their trend in the reactivity with Cr(VI) are comparable. To distinguish the speciation in chromium states, the IE-HPLC-ICP-MS analysis was performed. No Cr(III) was detected in the solution and the concentration of Cr(VI) is mimicking the trend of the decreasing Cr_{tot} concentration.

This corresponds with the results obtained by XPS (Fig. 5A–C), which confirm adsorption of the Cr(VI) onto the S-nZVI particle surface, followed by its reduction to Cr(III) and immobilization on the surface of S-nZVI in the form of chromium-iron (hydr)oxides (see above). Based on a detailed XPS analysis of the sulfur 2p core-level spectra after the experiment (24 h), all samples indicate the presence of sulfur in the oxidation state S²⁻, i.e. at a binding energy of 162.0 eV (Fig. 5D–F). The detection of SO₄²⁻ at a binding energy of approximately 168.7 eV suggests that sulfides, on the surface of S-nZVI, underwent the oxidation during the experiment, most likely as a result of interactions with aqueous environment and specifically with hexavalent chromium.

The evolution of pH, as monitor during the experiments followed generally the same trend for all the S-nZVI particles (Fig. S12F). Briefly, pH increased at the beginning of the experiment and reached the maximum value at the moment when Cr_{tot} was completely attached to the Fe atoms of the S-nZVI particles, remaining at the same level afterwards. In an opposite trend, Eh decreased rapidly at the beginning and remained almost the same throughout the whole experiment.

4. Conclusion and implications

The sulfidation of the activated air-stable nZVI particles with a core-shell architecture was successfully achieved across various Fe/S ratios, as confirmed by a combination of elemental analysis, XPS and HR-TEM results. This sulfidation process produced nanoparticles with high efficiency in degradation/elimination of Cr(VI) from the aqueous solution, which was comparable to that of conventionally sulfidated bare (and initially pyrophoric) nZVI particles.

In contrast, the non-activated nZVI particles exhibited limited effectiveness in Cr(VI) degradation/removal, even after sulfidation, highlighting the critical importance of activation of the air-stable nZVI particles prior to sulfidation process. The reaction of S-nZVI particles with hexavalent chromium led to the reduction of the Cr(VI) to Cr(III), followed by complexation with Fe atoms on the S-nZVI particle surface. This combined process resulted in the formation of mixed chromium-iron (hydr)oxides. The novel S-nZVI particles demonstrated its effectiveness not only in controlled experiments but also in treating contaminated groundwater.

These findings underscore the significant potential of sulfidated core-shell nZVI particles for innovative remediation technologies. Thus, the sulfidation of the activated air-stable nZVI particles represents a unique, safe and easily applicable procedural step that enhances the efficiency and accessibility of remediation processes while minimizing energy demand and hazardous waste generation. The air-stable nZVI particles can be easily transported to the contaminated sites in a form of a dry powder, mixed with water and left to undergo the activation over 24 to 48 h on-site. Sulfidation can then be achieved by simply adding a sulfidation agent to the suspension, producing highly reactive S-nZVI particles ready for immediate application into the contaminated groundwater.

Fig. 4. The residual concentrations of Cr_{tot} measured with ICP-MS (A) and Cr(VI) measured with IE-HPLC-ICP-MS (B) during the experiments with S-nZVI particles with S/Fe mass ratio of 0.01. The data are presented as the arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation of independently prepared triplicates (Cr_{tot}) and technical triplicates (total Cr(VI)).

Fig. 5. High-resolution XPS spectra from Cr 2p_{2/3} (A–C) and S 2p (D–F) regions collected from the following samples of S-nZVI_{NAC}, S-nZVI_{AC} and S-nZVI_P particles with S/Fe mass ratio equal to 0.01 after 24 h of interaction with Cr(VI) in the contaminated groundwater.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Viktorie Víchová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation. **Jana Krížek Oborná:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Martin Petr:** Visualization, Investigation. **Jana Soukupová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Radka Pechancová:** Investigation. **Tomáš Pluháček:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jan Filip:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data supporting this study are available in the ZENODO repository.

Acknowledgement

Authors gratefully acknowledge Jan Kolařík and Martin Lichovník for AAS measurements, Filip Gregar for ICP-MS analysis, Jana Stráská and Ondřej Tomanec for electron microscopy, Michaela Tomíčková for magnetic measurements, Petr Jakubec for EIS measurements and Ivo Medřík for technical support. The work was supported by ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE [grant number CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587] and the internal IGA grant of Palacký University [grant number IGA_PrF_2024_002, IGA_PrF_2024_026]. The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic [project number LM2023066].

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.106246>.

References

- D. O'Carroll, B. Sleep, M. Krol, H. Boparai, C. Kocur, Nanoscale zero valent iron and bimetallic particles for contaminated site remediation, *Adv. Water Resour.* 51 (2013) 104–122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.02.005>.
- L. Di, X. Chen, J. Lu, Y. Zhou, Y. Zhou, Removal of heavy metals in water using nano zero-valent iron composites: a review, *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 53 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2023.103913> (Elsevier Ltd.).
- W. Du, Y. Zhang, Y. Li, X. Ma, C. Zhao, A model for the removal of Cr(VI) in water by nanoscale zero-valent iron: quantifying the reaction process and calculating the electron efficiency, *J. Nanopart. Res.* 25 (6) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-023-05742-1>.
- M. Brumovský, J. Oborná, P. Lacina, M. Hegedúš, O. Sracek, J. Kolařík, M. Petr, J. Kašík, T. Hofmann, J. Filip, Sulfidated nano-scale zerovalent iron is able to effectively reduce in situ hexavalent chromium in a contaminated aquifer, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 405 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.124665>.
- T. Phenrat, N. Saleh, K. Sirk, R.D. Tilton, G. Lowry, v., Aggregation and sedimentation of aqueous nanoscale zerovalent iron dispersions, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 41 (1) (2007) 284–290, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es061349a>.
- D.S. Ken, A. Sinha, Recent developments in surface modification of nano zero-valent iron (nZVI): remediation, toxicity and environmental impacts, *Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring and Management* 14 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enmm.2020.100344> (Elsevier B.V.).
- J. Soukupova, R. Zboril, I. Medrik, J. Filip, K. Safarova, R. Ledl, M. Mashlan, J. Nosek, M. Cernik, Highly concentrated, reactive and stable dispersion of zero-valent iron nanoparticles: direct surface and site application, *Chem. Eng. J.* 262 (2015) 813–822, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2014.10.024>.
- J. Kašík, J. Kolařík, J. Filip, I. Medřík, O. Tomanec, M. Petr, O. Malina, R. Zboril, P. G. Tratnyek, Nanoarchitecture of advanced core-shell zero-valent iron particles with controlled reactivity for contaminant removal, *Chem. Eng. J.* 354 (2018) 335–345, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.08.015>.
- M. Brumovský, J. Filip, O. Malina, J. Oborná, O. Sracek, T.G. Reichenauer, P. Andryšková, R. Zboril, Core-shell Fe/fes nanoparticles with controlled shell thickness for enhanced trichloroethylene removal, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (31) (2020) 35424–35434, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c08626>.
- E. Petala, Y. Georgiou, V. Kostas, K. Dimos, M.A. Karakassides, Y. Deligiannakis, C. Aparicio, J. Tuček, R. Zboril, Magnetic carbon nanocages: an advanced architecture with surface- and morphology-enhanced removal capacity for arsenites, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 5 (7) (2017) 5782–5792, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.7b00394>.
- N.A. Awang, W.N. Wan Salleh, F. Aziz, N. Yusof, A.F. Ismail, A review on preparation, surface enhancement and adsorption mechanism of biochar-supported nano zero-valent iron adsorbent for hazardous heavy metals, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 98 (1) (2022) 22–44, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.7182> (John Wiley and Sons Ltd.).
- J. Němeček, P. Pokorný, O. Lhotský, V. Knytl, P. Najmanová, J. Steinová, M. Cerník, A. Filipová, J. Filip, T. Cajthaml, Combined nano-biotechnology for in-situ remediation of mixed contamination of groundwater by hexavalent chromium and chlorinated solvents, *Sci. Total Environ.* 563–564 (2016) 822–834, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.01.019>.
- M. Cerník, J. Nosek, J. Filip, J. Hrabal, D.W. Elliott, R. Zboril, Electric-field enhanced reactivity and migration of iron nanoparticles with implications for ground- water treatment technologies: proof of concept, *Water Res.* 154 (2019) 361–369, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.01.058>.
- D. Fan, Y. Lan, P.G. Tratnyek, R.L. Johnson, J. Filip, D.M. O'Carroll, A. Nunez Garcia, A. Agrawal, Sulfidation of iron-based materials: a review of processes and implications for water treatment and remediation, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 51 (22) (2017) 13070–13085, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b04177> (American Chemical Society).
- A.N. Garcia, Y. Zhang, S. Ghoshal, F. He, D.M. O'Carroll, Recent advances in sulfidated zerovalent iron for contaminant transformation, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (13) (2021) 8464–8483, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c01251> (American Chemical Society).
- S.R.C. Rajajayavel, S. Ghoshal, Enhanced reductive dechlorination of trichloroethylene by sulfidated nanoscale zerovalent iron, *Water Res.* 78 (2015) 144–153, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2015.04.009>.
- S.W. Park, S.K. Kim, J.B. Kim, S.W. Choi, H.I. Inyang, S. Tokunaga, Particle surface hydrophobicity and the dechlorination of chloro-compounds by iron sulfides, *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution: Focus* 6 (1–2) (2006) 97–110, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11267-005-9016-z>.
- J. Xu, Y. Wang, C. Weng, W. Bai, Y. Jiao, R. Kaegi, G. Lowry, v., Reactivity, selectivity, and long-term performance of sulfidized nanoscale zerovalent iron with different properties, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53 (10) (2019) 5936–5945, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b00511>.
- J. Li, X. Zhang, Y. Sun, L. Liang, B. Pan, W. Zhang, X. Guan, Advances in sulfidation of zerovalent iron for water decontamination, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 51 (23) (2017) 13533–13544, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b02695> (American Chemical Society).
- D. Li, Z. Mao, Y. Zhong, W. Huang, Y. Wu, P. Peng, Reductive transformation of tetrabromobisphenol A by sulfidated nano zerovalent iron, *Water Res.* 103 (2016) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.07.003>.
- J. Xu, Z. Cao, H. Zhou, Z. Lou, Y. Wang, X. Xu, G. Lowry, v., Sulfur dose and sulfidation time affect reactivity and selectivity of post-sulfidized nanoscale zerovalent iron, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53 (22) (2019) 13344–13352, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b04210>.
- Y. Su, A.S. Adeleye, A.A. Keller, Y. Huang, C. Dai, X. Zhou, Y. Zhang, Magnetic sulfide-modified nanoscale zerovalent iron (S-nZVI) for dissolved metal ion removal, *Water Res.* 74 (2015) 47–57, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2015.02.004>.
- L. Liang, X. Li, Z. Lin, C. Tian, Y. Guo, The removal of Cd by sulfidated nanoscale zero-valent iron: the structural, chemical bonding evolution and the reaction kinetics, *Chem. Eng. J.* 382 (2020) 122933, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.122933>.
- Y. Liu, J. Gao, Y. Wang, W. Duan, Y. Zhang, H. Zhang, M. Zhao, Synergistic effect of sulfidated nanoscale zerovalent iron in donor and recipient bacterial inactivation and gene conjugative transfer inhibition, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 432 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128722>.
- J. Yu, D. Liu, S. Yang, Y. Li, Reduction and stabilization of Cr (VI) in groundwater by using polysulfide-modified nanoscale zero-valent iron, *Appl. Geochem.* 145 (2022) 105428, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2022.105428>.
- Z. Cao, J. Xu, H. Li, T. Ma, L. Lou, G. Henkelman, X. Xu, Dechlorination and defluorination capability of sulfidized nanoscale zerovalent iron with suppressed water reactivity, *Chem. Eng. J.* 400 (2020) 125900, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.125900>.
- J. Xu, A. Avellan, H. Li, E.A. Clark, G. Henkelman, R. Kaegi, G.V. Lowry, Iron and sulfur precursors affect crystalline structure, speciation, and reactivity of sulfidized nanoscale zerovalent iron, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54 (20) (2020) 13294–13303, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c03879>.
- X. Hu, C. Chen, D. Chen, V. Noël, H. Oji, S. Ghoshal, J. Xu, Lattice engineered nanoscale Fe⁰ for selective reductions, *Nature Water* 2 (1) (2024) 84–92, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44221-023-00175-5>.
- C.E. Choong, S.Y. Yoon, K.T. Wong, M. Kim, G. Lee, S.H. Kim, B.H. Jeon, J. Choi, Y. Yoon, E.H. Choi, M. Jang, Hydrophobic sulfur core-shell layered metallic iron for nitrate reduction with nearly 100% dinitrogen selectivity: mechanism and field studies, *Chem. Eng. J.* 454 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.140083>.
- A.N. Garcia, H.K. Boparai, C.v. de Boer, A.I.A. Chowdhury, C.M.D. Kocur, L. M. Austrins, J. Herrera, D.M. O'Carroll, Fate and transport of sulfidated nano zerovalent iron (S-nZVI): a field study, *Water Res.* 170 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.115319>.
- J. Lederer, J. Filip, A. Ševců, M. Brumovský, N.H.A. Nguyen, J. Mikšíček, T. Sederer, A. Filipová, A. Filipová, J. Boháčková, J. Boháčková, T. Cajthaml, T. Cajthaml, Environmental fate of sulfidated nZVI particles: the interplay of nanoparticle corrosion and toxicity during aging, *Environ. Sci. Nano* 7 (6) (2020) 1794–1806, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0en00075b>.
- D.E. Kimbrough, Y. Cohen, A.M. Winer, L. Creelman, C. Mabuni, A critical assessment of chromium in the environment, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 29 (1) (1999) 1–46, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389991259164>.
- M. Bhattacharya, N.H. Barbhuiya, S.P. Singh, Performance evaluation of sulfidated nanoscale iron for hexavalent chromium removal from groundwater in sequential batch study, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 30 (59) (2023) 123055–123066, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-30960-4>.
- D. Lv, J. Zhou, Z. Cao, J. Xu, Y. Liu, Y. Li, X. Xu, Mechanism and influence factors of chromium (VI) removal by sulfide-modified nanoscale zerovalent iron, *Chemosphere* 224 (2019) 306–315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.02.109>.
- Y. Gong, L. Gai, J. Tang, J. Fu, Q. Wang, E.Y. Zeng, Reduction of Cr (VI) in simulated groundwater by FeS-coated iron magnetic nanoparticles, *Sci. Total Environ.* 595 (2017) 743–751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.282>.
- J. Gorny, G. Billon, C. Noiriél, D. Dumoulin, L. Lesven, B. Madé, Chromium behavior in aquatic environments: a review, *Environ. Rev.* 24 (4) (2016) 503–516, <https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2016-0012>.
- C.E. Barrera-Díaz, V. Lugo-Lugo, B. Bilyeu, A review of chemical, electrochemical and biological methods for aqueous Cr(VI) reduction. In, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 223–224 (2012) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2012.04.054>.
- Harboul, K., Aabedy, A. el, Hammami, K., & El-Karkouri, A. (2023). Reduction of hexavalent chromium using *Bacillus safensis* isolated from an abandoned mine. *Environ. Technol.*, 1–33. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2023.2256457>.

- [39] J. Iftthikar, I.I. Shahib, W. Jiang, R. Senthilnithy, Z. Elkhilfi, J. Wang, Z. Chen, Review on technologies for the development of effective and practical chromate removal from wastewaters, *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 11 (5) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110735> (Elsevier Ltd.).
- [40] S. Babel, T. Agustiono Kurniawan, Low-cost adsorbents for heavy metals uptake from contaminated water: a review, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 97 (2003), [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894\(02\)00263-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894(02)00263-7).
- [41] H. Li, X. Dong, E.B. da Silva, L.M. de Oliveira, Y. Chen, L.Q. Ma, Mechanisms of metal sorption by biochars: biochar characteristics and modifications, *Chemosphere* 178 (2017) 466–478, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.03.072> (Elsevier Ltd.).
- [42] P. Kajitvichyanukul, J. Ananattarachai, S. Pongpom, Sol-gel preparation and properties study of TiO₂ thin film for photocatalytic reduction of chromium(VI) in photocatalysis process, *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.* 6 (3–4 SPEC. ISS) (2005) 352–358, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stam.2005.02.014>.
- [43] Y. Lu, Y. Cai, S. Zhang, L. Zhuang, B. Hu, S. Wang, J. Chen, X. Wang, Application of biochar-based photocatalysts for adsorption-(photo)degradation/reduction of environmental contaminants: mechanism, challenges and perspective, *Biochar* 4 (1) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42773-022-00173-y> (Springer).
- [44] Z. Sun, M. Zhao, L. Chen, Z. Gong, J. Hu, D. Ma, Electrokinetic remediation for the removal of heavy metals in soil: limitations, solutions and prospect, *Sci. Total Environ.* 903 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165970> (Elsevier B.V.).
- [45] Z. Wang, X. He, X. Li, L. Chen, T. Tang, G. Cui, Q. Zhang, Y. Liu, Long-term stability and toxicity effects of three-dimensional electrokinetic remediation on chromium-contaminated soils, *Environ. Pollut.* 337 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.122461>.
- [46] P.C. Rathebe, L.G. Mosoeu, Fruits and vegetables contaminated with particles of heavy metals: a narrative review to explore the use of electromagnetic fields as an alternative treatment method, *Cogent Food and Agriculture* 9 (1) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2023.2231686>.
- [47] X. Chai, X. Qin, X. Gu, C. Ling, D. Lu, C. Zhang, Stability mechanism of hexavalent chromium reduction by nano-zerovalent iron under different environments, *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 234 (10) (2023) 617, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06606-z>.
- [48] D. Ribas, M. Černík, J.A. Benito, J. Filip, V. Marti, Activation process of air stable nanoscale zero-valent iron particles, *Chem. Eng. J.* 320 (2017) 290–299, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.03.056>.
- [49] U.S. EPA, Method 7196A: Chromium, Hexavalent (Colorimetric), SW-846 Third Edition, Update V, U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington DC, 1992.
- [50] J. Filip, F. Karlický, Z. Marušák, P. Lazar, M. Černík, M. Otyepka, R. Zboril, Anaerobic reaction of nanoscale zerovalent iron with water: mechanism and kinetics, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (25) (2014) 13817–13825, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp501846f>.
- [51] J. Xu, A. Avellan, H. Li, X. Liu, V. Noël, Z. Lou, G.V. Lowry, Sulfur loading and speciation control the hydrophobicity, electron transfer, reactivity, and selectivity of sulfidized nanoscale zerovalent iron, *Adv. Mater.* 32 (17) (2020) 1906910, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201906910>.
- [52] D. Turcio-Ortega, D. Fan, P.G. Tratnyek, E.J. Kim, Y.S. Chang, Reactivity of Fe/FeS nanoparticles: electrolyte composition effects on corrosion electrochemistry, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46 (22) (2012) 12484–12492, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es303422w>.
- [53] V.N. Montesinos, N. Quici, E.B. Halac, A.G. Leyva, G. Custo, S. Bengio, M.I. Litter, Highly efficient removal of Cr (VI) from water with nanoparticulated zerovalent iron: understanding the Fe (III)–Cr (III) passive outer layer structure, *Chem. Eng. J.* 244 (2014) 569–575, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2014.01.093>.
- [54] M.I. Litter, N. Quici, M. Meichtry (Eds.), *Iron Nanomaterials for Water and Soil Treatment*, CRC Press, 2018.
- [55] M.C. Biesinger, C. Brown, J.R. Mycroft, R.D. Davidson, N.S. McIntyre, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy studies of chromium compounds, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 36 (12) (2004) 1550–1563, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.1983>.